

Figure S1. Plateau curves for optimal incubation time variation.

Figure S1. FI_{Sample-Blank} (*y*-axis) versus cell concentration (*x*-axis) for all levels of confluency (very low, low-medium, and medium-high). FI is expressed as arbitrary units (au). Error bars indicate SD. Incubation time longer than **A)** 4 hours (h), **B)** 2h and **C)** 1h.